

Modular Integrated Ecocriticism Literature: A Proposed Approach to Teaching Post-Haiyan Poetry

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Abstract: This qualitative study aimed to integrated post-Haiyan poetry in teaching ecocriticism literature through modular approach. Specifically, this study aims to: a. recognize the educational value of an eco-literature in terms of transmission of feelings and messages on environmental degradation; b. extraction of the root causes of environmental crisis; c. promotion of eco-consciousness on environmental values and issues; and, d. development of ecological or environmental literacy. It also sought to identify what teaching methodologies and techniques can be utilized; determine what learning activities can be suggested; and, develop a proposed learning material. Teaching post-Haiyan poetry can certainly encapsulates the recollected feelings and sentiments. Using ecocriticism theory in environmental literature, students can unearth not just the deep feelings and messages on environmental degradation but also explore the causes of environmental crisis. Awareness can be derived and used as a spring-board to let people think twice on their actions towards the environment. Also, environmental literacy can be developed through understanding people's place on Earth and the importance of nature to them as it provide us with useful enlightenment on how to handle the relationship between man and nature. Teaching approaches were suggested to use in teaching Ecocriticism such as Personal Growth Model, Moral-Philosophical Approach, Information-based Approach, Personal response-based Approach, Thematic Approach, Group Approach, Response Approach, and Problem-posing Approach. In teaching methods, Criticism method, Discussion method, Discovery method, Activity method and Read and Explain method though related to discussion method can also be used. To make learning interactive, Information-Based Activities like comprehension questions exercises, lecture sessions, and read notes from workbooks/handouts with students was suggested. Personal-Response Activities such as explain a text to students, journal writing, brainstorming sessions, small group discussions and writing about feelings/reactions towards an issue. Moral-Philosophical Activities like reflective sessions, discussions on moral dilemmas, tell moral values to students and conduct self-evaluation activities can be used. Other activities can be also useful like concept mapping, student-teacher discussion, and discussion of a topic with a partner, group discussion, film viewing, role-playing, reflective essays, and storytelling. A learning module was developed to aid literature teachers in teaching ecocriticism theory. The material can help students in understanding ecocriticism theory and the importance of studying environmental-related literature. The module also contains discussion on the four guide post used by Acompañado et. al. study in analyzing eco-literature. A guide on how to make an environmental-related literature critique was also included.

Keywords: ecocriticism theory, modular approach, post-Haiyan poetry, Samaron literature.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching and studying literature offers unique insights into the changing ways in which humans have interacted with the rest of the physical world. Literature transforms our perceptions and the role of imagination in confronting some of the world's most urgent problems such as an immense environmental crisis, with destructive consequences to its climate, wildlife, forests, oceans, and many human societies. How can we understand the causes of that crisis? How can we

understand the challenges of environmentalism and sustainability? How can we provide alternatives? How can we persuade young minds to listen to the cries of our Mother Nature? What is the truth of ecology addressed by literature? And how does literature address that truth?

Hence, this study aimed to integrate environmental-related literature in classroom instruction, not just to spread environmental awareness and concern but to give importance to Ecocriticism as a literary movement. Curriculum planners and designers should incorporate it in literature classes where in-depth analysis and understanding of poetry and other realms of literary genres are studied. Post-Haiyan poems, for example, are embedded with environmental lessons and communicates the harsh reality that human brought to themselves and to nature. Through studying environment-related literature, human eco-consciousness is awoken. Thus, it should be included in developing lessons and syllabi.

Moreover, literature offers a great resource of interaction between humans and environment. However, as what the researcher have observed, only few are interested in unearthing the literary works of our folk people through the use of Ecocriticism theory - an approach which, the researcher also noticed, is not given much attention and importance compared to other literary theories. This resulted to unavailability and lack of instructional materials and resources in teaching Ecocriticism Literature. To respond to inadequate learning resources in teaching eco-literature and to address the call for effective instructional materials, this mini-research aimed to create a proposed module in understanding and analyzing environmental-related literature as an output of the study which can be used both by literature teachers and students.

This research can serve as a useful material that can be incorporated in teaching literature. Ultimately, it is the researcher's intention to pursue further research to look at the current dearth of eco-critical approaches to literature and the potential for interconnected thinking on sustainability: literary analysis, the educational milieu, and social and ecological issues. Through this study, literature teachers and students can grasp opportune issues that will open vistas of understanding. It will also make them realize that there is a rich reservoir of poetry locally. It will also offer immersion in the rich Samaron literature. This will give both teachers and students an opportunity to study the writing styles of our local writers and experience their local heritage.

Furthermore, pedagogically oriented courses can greatly benefit from the values that can be elicited from the environmental-related literature. Post-Haiyan poems, for example, instill values, pasture environmental awareness and deepen understanding of disasters. It is not only admired for their aesthetic structure or creative aspect, but they are also admired for their moralizing properties. The humanities offers as a leeway for human discovery and reflection. As a result, literature works as a way to bridge the two separate planes of environmental perception and value laden resources.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

In this study, modular-integrated ecocriticism literature as a proposed approach to teaching post-Haiyan poetry generally intends to uncover the relationship of human and nature.

Specifically, this study aims to:

1. recognize the educational value of an eco-literature in terms of:
 - a. transmission of feelings and messages on environmental degradation;
 - b. extraction of the root causes of environmental crisis;
 - c. promotion of eco-consciousness on environmental values and issues; and,
 - d. development of ecological or environmental literacy.
2. identify what teaching methodologies and techniques can be utilized;
3. determine what learning activities can be suggested; and,
4. develop a proposed learning material.

III. METHODOLOGY

The primary aim of this paper is to develop a set of modules for eco-literature class using the analyses of five (5) Post-Haiyan poems that contain societal and environmental issues. Hence, this research is a qualitative study that will employ instructional design method of research. The qualitative approach is most suited in this study as it will enable the

researcher to derive a full understanding on the educational value of an eco-literature in terms of: transmission of feelings and messages on environmental degradation; extraction of the root causes of environmental crisis; promotion of eco-consciousness on environmental values and issues; and, development of ecological or environmental literacy. It will also aid the researcher in answering what teaching methodologies and techniques can be utilized and what learning activities can be suggested.

In addition, since the data that will be used in this study is a textual analyses of five (5) Post-Haiyan poetry conducted by Acompañado, et. al., the researcher found no suitable qualitative methodologies to utilize in the current research.

In connection, Instructional Design can be defined as the creation of instructional materials, modules or lessons (Kurt, 2017). It is the systematic process of translating a plan of instruction into a set of activities, materials, information and/or assessment procedures (Smith & Ragan, 2005). According to Kelly (2013), design-based research is indicated when one or more of the following conditions are present:

- When the content knowledge to be learned is new or [is] being discovered even by the experts.
- When how to teach the content is unclear: pedagogical content knowledge is poor.
- When the instructional materials are poor or not available.
- When the teachers' knowledge and skills are unsatisfactory.
- When the educational researchers' knowledge of the content and instructional strategies or instructional materials are poor.
- When complex societal, policy or political factors may negatively affect progress.

In the above conditions, instructional design is therefore suitable to employ in developing the learning material.

In developing the module, the researcher will try to utilize Robert Gagne's Nine Events of Instruction (1965) which is based on the behaviorist approach to learning. Gagne identified the Nine Events of Instruction as follows:

1. Gain the student's attention. Emotional buy-in is the first step in laying the foundation for learning retention. This can be done by telling a story or asking a thought-provoking question.
2. Inform students of the objectives. Establishes expectations for the course and criteria for measuring success or failure.
3. Stimulate recall of prior learning. Leverages existing knowledge as a scaffold to incorporate new knowledge.
4. Present the content. Use chunking for easy consumption of the content.
5. Provide learner guidance. Supplement the content with case studies, activities, discussion questions and other instructional support materials.
6. Elicit performance. Challenge learner's activities that recall, utilize, and evaluate knowledge.
7. Provide feedback. Use immediate feedback to reinforce knowledge.
8. Assess performance. Test learner knowledge against established criteria.
9. Enhance retention and transfer to job. Use content retention strategies to appropriate job aids to retain new knowledge.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In his critical writing "Literature and Ecology: An Experiment in Ecocriticism" in 1978, William Rueckert first coined the term ecocriticism. The word 'eco' comes from the Greek root word 'oikos' which etymologically means household or earth and 'logy' from 'logos' means logical discourse. It means 'criticism of the house-the environment as represented in literature.' According to Rueckert, ecocriticism applies ecology or ecological principles into the study of literature. In the same manner, Lawrence Buell defines ecocriticism "as a study of the relationship between literature and the environment conducted in a spirit of commitment to environmentalist's praxis." Moreover, Patrick D. Murphy said that Ecocriticism is literary "criticism that arises from and is oriented toward a concern with human and nonhuman interaction and interrelationship" (Mishra, 2017).

The growing awareness of widespread environmental crisis has brought to humanities studies a broad new range of “greening” approaches. A modernized teaching methodology has been gradually realized, which focuses on integrated and interdisciplinary teaching approach. This establishes the strategic foundation of the implementation of ecocriticism in teaching literature. Integrating Ecocriticism in teaching literature can certainly provide the following education value:

a. Transmission of Feelings and Messages on Environmental Degradation

Environmental literature, like Post-Haiyan poetry, can exhibit feelings of love, nostalgia, worry, remorse, confusion, pity, desperation, fear and anger. In the study of Acompañado, et.al. (2018), it was revealed that the selected post-Haiyan poems carry the sentiments and feelings of the speakers about the disaster. Environmental literary pieces encapsulate the Typhoon Haiyan survivors’ recollected feelings and sentiments. It transmit their struggles with nature and center on how people contemplate upon their atrocity after the disaster.

Moreover, it can also express sadness and grief over people’s losses. It can reveal people’s negative human feelings and unveil positive feelings toward the disaster. Eco-literature depicts how a disaster destroys the environment and the lives of people but it also teach people how to appreciate nature’s beauty and importance. It can develop love for nature that thereby espouse environmental awareness and concern. It can make people contemplate that preserving the nature’s ecology and protecting its natural beauty are responsibilities that everyone should act upon. Hence, the post-Haiyan poetry awakens the eco-consciousness of people through extracting the feelings conveyed in the poems.

b. Extraction of the Root Causes of Environmental Crisis

According to Mishra (2017), environment has posed a great threat to human society as well as the Mother Earth. The extensive misuse of natural resources has left us at the brink of ditch. The rainforests are cut down, the fossil fuel is fast decreasing, the cycle of season is at disorder, ecological disaster is frequent now round the globe and our environment is at margin. Hence, through using ecocriticism theory in environmental literature can unearth not just deep feelings and messages on environmental degradation but also explore the causes of environmental crisis.

The causes of crisis are primarily because of human atrocities and anthropocentric perspective towards nature. Our global crisis is not because how ecosystems function. The present environmental crisis is a bi-product of human culture. It is because how our ethical systems function. Getting through the crisis requires understanding our impact on nature. It requires understanding those ethical systems and using that understanding to reform them. By integrating ecocriticism in literature class, it can elevate the students’ environmental consciousness and awareness and thereby act upon the problem as the future stewards of Mother Earth.

c. Promotion of Eco-Consciousness on Environmental Values and Issues

The earth is lodged at the verge of a rigorous environmental crisis. Current environmental problems make people vulnerable to disasters and tragedies. However, if people address the various issues discerningly and with seriousness, it is undisputable that there is still a chance for environmental recovery. Ecocriticism is characterized by eco-consciousness. In short, it is an earth centric approach to literary studies which promotes the understanding of who we are, where we stand, and how we should behave with our Mother Nature. In order to address the present environmental crisis, teachers and the eco-critics play an important role in building up the eco-consciousness among students and readers. Criticizing environmental literature can be of help in interpreting unsurfaced meanings rather than just analyzing first layer facts. Through classroom integration, awareness can be derived and used as a spring-board to let the people think twice on their actions towards the environment.

d. Development of Ecological or Environmental Literacy

Environmental oriented study of literature brings about an ecological literacy among the readers who in the process become eco-conscious, thereby taking good care of Mother Nature. If we employ a new critical approach eco-criticism to interpret literature, then it is particularly appropriate to an examination of literature in the context of globally environmental predicament and arouse the modern people's consciousness. Besides, it provides us with useful enlightenment on how to handle the relationship between man and nature, at the same time arouse the reader's ecological consciousness. In a world much burdened with the wide spread ecological crisis, the emergence of ecocriticism had signaled a new and promising hermeneutical horizon in our interpretations and understandings of the natural world and literature.

Studying and teaching ecocriticism underlines environmental justice as man's voracious urge to conquer nature is somewhat misleading. Environmental literacy can be developed through understanding people's place on Earth and the importance of nature to them. People used to believe that they are superior to the other life forms that inhabit the biosphere. However, they now realize that nature is not a subordinate but a co-inhabitant of this earth ecosystem. All organisms on this earth have their own intrinsic values and no one is the master of anybody. This realization will give equal rights to every organism maintaining a balance in the eco-system. Therefore, ecocriticism gives emphasis on this eco-consciousness removing the ego-consciousness man. This will then develop the ecological or environmental literacy of people.

Teaching Approaches, Methodologies and Techniques to utilize in Ecocriticism Literature

Edward (1965) placed in a hierarchy with the operational key that techniques carry out a method which is consistent with an approach. By definition, approach is viewed as "a set of correlative assumptions dealing with the nature of teaching and learning a subject and as a theoretical or ideological concept which underlies a peculiar way of teaching a given subject". It describes the nature of the subject matter to be taught. Furthermore, Edward says that "approach states a point of view, a philosophy, an article of faith – i.e. something one believes but cannot necessarily prove, often unarguable except in terms of the effectiveness of the method that grow out of it (Ikonne, 2016).

Method, on the other hand, is meant as "an overall plan for orderly presentation of subject material." It is systematic and procedural and to be used by teachers who know it. It is based on a selected approach. Ubahakwe also defined method as the "systematic, predictable procedure of teaching". According to him, it includes selection and ordering of teaching contexts, a specification of the roles of the teacher as well as of the learners in the classroom encounter, a specification of the types and functions of the teaching materials in a given situation. In one approach, there may be many methods (Ikonne, 2016).

Approaches

Savvidou (2006) notes that Carter and Long put forward three main approaches used to teach literature, i.e. The Cultural Model, The Language Model and *The Personal Growth Model*. However, in teaching Ecocriticism Literature, the Personal Growth Model is suitable to utilize as it uses the text as stimulus for discussion in support of reflection and personal growth activities. This model encourages the learners to express their opinions, feelings and make connections between their own personal and cultural experience and those expressed in the text. Learning therefore is said to take place when readers are able to interpret a text and construct meaning on the basis of their experience (Sidhu & Chan Yuen Fook, 2010).

Another approach suitable to teaching ecocriticism literature is *Moral-Philosophical Approach* aims to integrate more humanistic values among the students. It is also suitable to use in teaching ecocriticism literature. Using this approach, teacher can incorporate moral values in lessons, ask students the values they learn from the text, get students to search moral values from a text, and raise students' awareness of values derived from the text (Mustakim et. al.).

Moreover, Rosli (1995) proposes three main approaches to literature teaching; information-based approaches, personal response-based approaches and language-based approaches (Muthusamy, et. al. 2017). Integrating ecocriticism theory in teaching post-Haiyan poetry would be effective if information-based approach and personal response-based approach is employed. The following explains the two approaches:

Information-based approach is used to teach knowledge about literature and treat literature mainly as a source of facts or information about a target culture. Here, the teacher can use this approach to elicit information from students about the text, explain the content of the text to the class, ask questions to check students' knowledge based on what they have read and provide students with background information. However, the drawback here is that the teaching methodologies used tend to be teacher-centered and reading is largely for information.

It is highly suggested to also incorporate *Personal response-based approach* as it is more student-centered. This approach focuses on eliciting individual response to a text. The approach is to motivate students to read by relating the themes and topics in the text to his or her-own personal experience. Savvidou, (2004) identifies personal growth model as reader-response approach. Its emphasis is on question discussion methodologies (Muthusamy, et. al. 2017). Here, the teacher can encourage students to relate the themes to personal experiences, Elicit students' response to a text, Encourage students to express feelings towards the issues of the text.

There are also some approaches to teaching literature which can be applied. It depends on what the teacher thinks is suitable and appropriate to use in a certain literary text. Some of them are as follows (Ikonne, 2016):

Thematic approach: This is the teaching of literature based on the understanding of the central theme and the sub themes.

Group Approach: This engages the weak and the strong in a common activity possibly to strengthen the weak. As an approach to teaching of literature, group approach is engaged in to dramatize or act out the text.

Response Approach: This portrays the critical method. This offers the student the freedom to be real to the text and not stereotyped or stage-managed.

Problem posing approach requires the students to unravel a given mystery in the text.

Methods

Teaching methods is the general principles, pedagogy and management strategies used for classroom instruction. Teachers' method depends on what fits their educational philosophy, classroom, demographic, and subject areas/s. Ikonne (2016) also suggested some methods in teaching literature.

Criticism method: This is highly recommended in literature teaching. Students may be occasionally required to criticize the information they obtain from the "Study Guides" with close reference to the actual text. This method prompts student to read further for more information. This is capable of evoking and sustaining the interest of the students in the subject.

Discussion method: This could be an effective means of ensuring that students read the text and acquire the correct information.

Discovery method: This stems from problem posing approach and can achieve greater result when fused with discussion method. Here, the teacher can identify some of the contemporary issues raised in the text under study and encourage the students to propose solutions bearing in mind the evidence contained in the text. This encourages originality and flexibility of ideas or thoughts. It also to encourage initiatives and curiosity, questioning method is encouraged.

Activity method: This can be best portrayed with dramatization technique which is great value to the teaching of literature.

Read and explain method though related to discussion method, is also a good method that challenges the students.

Techniques

The teacher can develop a variety of techniques to facilitate the teaching and learning of literature. The teacher's techniques would be determined by a number of factors viz; the age of the learners, the environment where the teaching/learning takes place, the text to be read, availability of material resources and of course the time available to the class. (Ikonne, 2016).

Guidelines for Literature Teaching in Singapore Secondary Schools (1989) explores some techniques of teaching poetry that involved pre-reading techniques (for example: draw pupils into the text, activate background knowledge, relate the text to personal experiences), techniques of sustaining reading and exploration (for example: divide the work into manageable portions, provide motivation for independent reading, provide a framework), and techniques for highlighting and follow-up (for examples: explore a particular theme or character, enable pupils to express their own response, enable pupils to share views or ideas) process (Rohaniyah, 2012).

Moreover, Wu & Wu (2008) stated that the applying particular techniques and approach in teaching and learning literature such as student-centered activities, teaching and learning literature can be an enjoyable, exciting, and uplifting experience because the reading process provokes students' individual thoughts and interpretations. The literature classroom should be a place where dissimilar ideas confront, conflict, and at times converge with each other, for students will gain maximum profit only when they are active and highly-involved in the learning process (Rohaniyah, 2012).

Learning Activities that can be used for Teaching Ecocriticism Literature

Learning activities play an important role in making teaching effective. Also, the activities designed or deployed by the teachers brings or creates the condition for learning. Some common activities used in teaching the literature subjects were dramatization and role-playing, lecture and reporting, paint the picture, report, group works, sharing of experiences, summary of selection, reflection, pantomime, opera, puppets, shadow play.

In addition, *Information-Based Activities* like comprehension questions exercises, lecture sessions, and read notes from workbooks/handouts with students. In *Personal-Response Activities*, teachers can utilize activities such as explain a text to students, journal writing, brainstorming sessions, small group discussions and writing about feelings/reactions towards an issue. Teaching ecocriticism literature aims to make students aware of the environmental issues and concern. So, *Moral-Philosophical Activities* like reflective sessions, discussions on moral dilemmas, tell moral values to students and conduct self-evaluation activities can be used.

Other interactive activities can also be employed like *concept mapping*. It gives the students a clear mind flow of the story because it is easier to determine the sequence of events. Concept mapping facilitates the learning process by allowing the instructor to identify missing or irrelevant concepts, trivial or incorrect linking phrases, etc. The concept map provides the basis for discussions between students and their instructors, to clarify relationships such as the one depicted, and generally to gain a better understanding of the subject matter.

Student-teacher discussion is popular among teachers and learners for the purpose of brainstorming or listening to opinions. It is very important that in order to take place there must be exchange of ideas between the teacher and the students. This kind of interaction implies that the students are curious to find answers and teachers find ways to make the discussion noteworthy.

Discussion of a topic with a partner. Here, a student talks about his ideas with his peer. Together they analyze, review, clarify and sometimes correct each other's work. As Pierce (2009) cited, this can help to clarify and reinforce the reviewers' knowledge and understanding of the area and encourages the development of advanced critical thinking and higher-order cognitive skills.

Group discussion. Teachers encourage students to participate in groups. According to Loser, in initiating this activity, the teacher assigns problems to heterogeneous groups of five to seven students and facilitates collaboration to solve the problems. Members of the group will have different knowledge and skills to contribute, so the groups will tend to solve problems better than the individual members can on their own. In the process, students will learn knowledge, skills, and strategies from each other, especially if you have them discuss the processes they used.

Film viewing appeals to teachers and students as a form of entertainment.

Role-playing is one way of expressing emotions of the students. Through this, they experience things that are new to them.

Reflective essays stimulate students to express their personal experiences. Other topics that students compose denote description of characters, analyzing events, theme, and lesson learned.

Storytelling using visual aids are also interesting and very effective. Because of its nature, teachers are enlightened with the students' creativity. On one hand, both teachers and students experience the pleasure of listening to personal stories, anecdotes, and unforgettable tales. This confirms what Sialongo (2010) says that Literature is a product of a particular culture that concretizes man's array of values, emotions, actions and ideas.

As observed, these learning activities generate positive student response and a good springboard in understanding the literary texts. The interesting and effective learning activities in studying literature are considered practicable in analyzing literary texts.

In teaching ecocriticism literature, the objective of teaching held important role. The successful of the teaching is measured for how far the objective of teaching can be reached in teaching and learning process.

To achieve the objectives of teaching, the teachers implement methods, techniques/ strategies, approaches, and procedures or choose the effective and appropriate ways in their teaching. The uses of particular techniques of teaching literature in each form of literary works are very useful. The appropriate methods, approaches, and techniques for teaching poetry enable students to increase their competence both in language and literature. Literature as content subject has given several functions to the students in the learning process. Literary texts also have a powerful function in raising moral and ethical concerns in the classroom (Rohaniyah, 2012). Hence:

"Literature has great function in developing human's feelings, ideas, and interests. In specific, the functions of literature are as follows: the first function is literature gives knowledge of those particularities with which science and philosophy

are not concerned. The second function is that literature makes the human perceive what human see, imagine what human already know conceptually or practically. The final function of literature is that literature relieve human either writers or readers from the pressure of emotions.”

Teaching is dynamic and through time, changes in strategies is evolving. Traditional lecture may inspire one student but may also frustrate the others. Thus, different types of learners needs various tasked-based strategies to enthuse them. According to Ugochi Happiness Ikonne in *The Teaching of Literature: Approaches and Methods* (2016), lack of interest in the study of literature has given rise to lack of linguistic, communicative and discourse competence among students and graduates of nowadays. In the cradle of education and in the ancient times, the study of literature particularly poetry and rhetoric was of paramount importance. Accordingly, the ancient system produced strong orators who were proficient in all sphere of endeavor; administration, politics and legal to mention but a few. Today, little or no attention is paid to poetry as a genre of literature. Hence, teachers must learn, adopt, and use teaching strategies in their day to day lessons in the classroom for them to be effective. Effective teachers are also expected to make their learners responsive to the future societal roles they may take.

This is supported by Mulligan (2011) who pointed out that effective teaching requires ‘flexibility and creativity, constant monitor and adjustment’ of the teaching techniques. Knutson (2014) on the other hand pointed out that choosing the appropriate approaches in teaching and how these approaches are done is pertinent to students’ learning. Bay (2012) maintained that the success of the teaching strategy depends on the frequency of its use in the classroom. Center to Teaching Learning (2014) found that teaching effective teaching does not only involve the utilization of tools, techniques, and strategies but also the comprehension of meanings specifically on how students learn, process information, motivates themselves, and the things which hinders learning (San Jose, et. al. 2015).

Learning Material that can be suggested in teaching Ecocriticism Literature

Module

The trend of using modules as teaching-learning approach is becoming very popular in recent times. Modular teaching approach is an extension and advanced shape of programmed instruction/learning. In this approach the teacher uses teaching modules prepared for specific purposes instead of traditional textbook. Module as a unit of teaching activity and learning expressed as an approximate number of hours of study. The module will be self-contained although certain combinations of modules may represent a progression through the curriculum. This change is due to the reason that in about last decade learning theories have moved from a stimulus-response point to information processing. It assists students in understanding complex and difficult concepts. In educational context, now the shift has moved from traditional teaching approach to modular teaching approach.

Modular approach dates from B.F. Skinner’s and others’ research in 1950s which led to the formulation of different principles of teaching and which later on became main characteristics of programmed instruction such as division of subject matter into small steps, active participation of students, immediate feedback, and self-pacing. These are all the principles that are used in modules’ making.

Moon (1988) describes that the modular studies syllabus seeks to facilitate an approach to learning, which is experiential, practical, and related to life in the community and wider world. The differences can be shown more systematically by identifying key conditions for effective learning and comparing how these conditions are met or not met by conventional teaching and by modular instruction (Meyer, 1988). Modular approach has proven to be an effective and efficient tool to help students learn. Most subjects can be taught with this approach (Malik, 2012).

The mode of teaching and learning during pandemic has changed. Literature teachers are also challenged on how to make learning interactive. It is the aim of this research to somehow lessen the difficulty; hence, with the help of the researcher’s proposed module in teaching literature specifically environmental literature, teaching ecocriticism will be easy.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Integrating Ecocriticism in teaching literature can certainly provide education value such as transmission of feelings and messages on environmental degradation environmental literature. Teaching post-Haiyan poetry, for example, can exhibit feelings of love, nostalgia, worry, remorse, confusion, pity, desperation, fear and anger. It can encapsulates the recollected feelings and sentiments. It transmit their struggles with nature and center on how people contemplate upon their atrocity

after the disaster. It can also extract the root causes of environmental crisis. Using ecocriticism theory in environmental literature, students can unearth not just the deep feelings and messages on environmental degradation but also explore the causes of environmental crisis. In promotion of eco-consciousness on environmental values and issues, criticizing environmental literature can be of help in interpreting unsurfaced meanings rather than just analyzing first layer facts. Through classroom integration, awareness can be derived and used as a spring-board to let the people think twice on their actions towards the environment. Development of ecological or environmental literacy can also be drawn in the literary texts. Environmental literacy can be developed through understanding people's place on Earth and the importance of nature to them. Environmental oriented study of literature brings about an ecological literacy among the readers who in the process become eco-conscious, thereby taking good care of Mother Nature. It provides us with useful enlightenment on how to handle the relationship between man and nature, at the same time arouse the reader's ecological consciousness.

Various teaching approaches, methodologies and techniques can also be utilized in teaching Ecocriticism Literature. Teaching approaches was suggested such as Personal Growth Model, Moral-Philosophical Approach, Information-based Approach, Personal response-based Approach, Thematic Approach, Group Approach, Response Approach, and Problem-posing Approach. In teaching methods, Criticism method, Discussion method, Discovery method, Activity method and Read and Explain method though related to discussion method can also be used.

To make learning interactive, activities were also suggested. Information-Based Activities like comprehension questions exercises, lecture sessions, and read notes from workbooks/handouts with students. In Personal-Response Activities, teachers can utilized activities such as explain a text to students, journal writing, brainstorming sessions, small group discussions and writing about feelings/reactions towards an issue. Moral-Philosophical Activities like reflective sessions, discussions on moral dilemmas, tell moral values to students and conduct self-evaluation activities can be used. Other interactive activities can also be employed like concept mapping, student-teacher discussion, and discussion of a topic with a partner, group discussion, film viewing, role-playing, reflective essays, and storytelling.

A learning module was also developed and proposed. The material can aid literature teachers in teaching ecocriticism theory. For students, the material is also helpful in understanding ecocriticism theory and the importance of studying environmental-related literature. The module also contains discussion on the four guide post used by Acompañado et. al. study in analyzing eco-literature. A guide on how to make an environmental-related literature critique was also included.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aggabao, Rischelle G. & Guiab, Marissa R. "Learning Activities in Studying Literature." Journal Article. International Refereed Research Journal Vol.-V, Issue – 3. Retrieved on June 29, 2021 https://www.academia.edu/29037039/LEARNING_ACTIVITIES_IN_STUDYING_LITERATURE. July 2014.
- [2] Anisa, Hainur, et .al. Development of Poetry Writing Learning Module Assisted by Religious Songs for Junior High School UNIVA Medan. Journal Article. Atlantis Press, Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research, Vol. 384. Retrieved on June 22, 2021. <https://www.atlantis-press.com/proceedings/aisteel-19/125928459>. December 2019.
- [3] Aniver Masinsin Vergara, Development, Effectiveness and Acceptability of Module for the Problem Solving and Critical Thinking Skills of Alternative Learning System in District of Tanay II, Research. Research Gate, Retrieved on June 22, 2021. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/329771095_DEVELOPMENT_OF_MODULE. September 19, 2017.
- [4] Barriga, Torres and Trinidad, María. Eco-Didactics: Applying Ecocriticism and Environmental Issues in Secondary Education. Journal Article. UNIVERSIDAD DE JAÉN, Centro de Estudios de Postgrado, Retrieved on June 29, 2021. <http://tauja.ujaen.es/bitstream/10953.1/2592/1/MAR%C3%8DA%20TRINIDAD%20TORRES%20BARRIGA.pdf>. July 2015.
- [5] Buell, Lawrence et, al. "Literature and Environment" Journal Article. Annual Review of Environment and Resources, doi: 10.1146/annurev-environ-111109-144855. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. <https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/pdf/10.1146/annurev-environ-111109-144855>. August 1, 2011.
- [6] Fenn, Dr.Vathana. "Roots of Ecocriticism: An Exploration of the History of Ecocriticism, A Literary Theory of the Post-Modern World. Research Article. Veda's Journal of English Language and Literature (JOELL), Vol.2 Issue 2. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. <http://joell.in/wp-content/uploads/2015/08/Ecocriticism1.pdf>. 2015.

- [7] Friestad-Tate, Jill et. al. Understanding Modular Learning - Developing A Strategic Plan To Embrace Change. Journal Article. I-manager's Journal on School Educational Technology, Vol. 9, No. 4. Retrieved on June 22, 2021. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1097629>. March-May 2014.
- [8] Garrard, Greg. "Ecocriticism and Education for Sustainability." Journal Article. Pedagogy: Critical Approaches to Teaching Literature, Language, Composition, and Culture. Volume 7, Number 3 doi: 10.1215/15314200-2007-005. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. Duke University Press. https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/33813820/Ecocriticism_and_Education_for_Sustainable_Development.pdf. 2007.
- [9] Guanio-Uluru, Lykke. "Education for Sustainability: Developing Ecocritical Literature Circles in the Student Teacher Classroom." Journal Article. Discourse and Communication for Sustainable Education, vol.10, no.1, doi: 10.2478/dcse-2019-0002. Retrieved on June 29, 2021, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333778062_Education_for_Sustainability_Developing_Ecocritical_Literature_Circles_in_the_Student_Teacher_Classroom. 2019.
- [10] Ikonne, Ugochi Happiness. The Teaching of Literature: Approaches and Methods. IIARD – International Institute of Academic Research and Development. ISSN 2489-0073 Vol. 2 No.5. 2016
- [11] Jimmy, Neema Bagula. "Ecocritical Approach to Literary Text Interpretation." Journal Article. International Journal of Innovation and Scientific Research. ISSN 2351-8014 Vol. 18 No., pp. 369-378. Retrieved on June 29, 2021 <http://www.issrjournals.org/links/papers.php?journal=ijisr&application=pdf&article=IJISR-15-155-03>. Oct. 2, 2015.
- [12] Mishra, Sandip Kumar. "Ecocriticism: A Study of Environmental Issues in Literature." Journal Article. BRICS Journal of Educational Research, 6(4), 168-170. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/318350741_Ecocriticism_A_Study_of_Environmental_Issues_in_Literature/link/59650d314585157fcc5e35f6/download. 2016.
- [13] Mohd, Chitra Muthusamy Syahaizad et.al. "Methods Used in Teaching and Learning of Literature in the ESL Classroom and Adult Learners' Attitude." Journal Article. Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research Volume 4, Issue 2. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314237370_Methods_Used_in_Teaching_and_Learning_of_Literature_in_the_ESL_Classroom_and_Adult_Learners'_Attitude. 2017.
- [14] Rashid, Haroon Ur et. al. Development and Validation of Module for Teaching Human Rights at Higher Education Level. Journal Research Article. Sir Syed Journal of Education & Social Research Vol. 3, Issue 2, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.36902/sjesr-vol3-iss2-2020> (182-189). Retrieved on June 22, 2021. https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/9f6e/d65d91931ac9b085f34e537b91467b9c04d3.pdf?_ga=2.92559774.2011218443.1624332499-1381432750.1571279645. April-June 2020.
- [15] San Jose, Ariel E. and Galang, Jerlyn G. "Teaching Strategies in Teaching Literature: Students in Focus." Journal Article. International Journal of Education and Research Vol. 3 No. 4, Retrieved on June 29, 2021. https://www.academia.edu/38116330/TEACHING_STRATEGIES_IN_TEACHING_LITERATURE_STUDENTS_IN_FOCUS. April 2015.
- [16] Sidhu, Gurnam Kaur, et.al. "Instructional Practices in Teaching Literature: Observations of ESL Classrooms in Malaysia." Journal Article. English Language Teaching Vol. 3, No. 2. Retrieved on June 29, 2021 <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1081570.pdf>. June 2010.
- [17] Tripathi, Mallika et, al. "An Analysis of Eco-criticism and Literature with special reference to the works of Hardy and Dickens." Journal Article. International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities, Volume IV. Issue III, Retrieved on June 29, 2021. https://www.academia.edu/33673805/An_Analysis_of_Ecocriticism_and_Literature_with_special_reference_to_the_works_of_Hardy_and_Dickens. March 2016,
- [18] Van Anh, Ho Thi. "Building Environmental Awareness through Implementation of Ecocriticism in Literature Teaching." Journal Article. Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research (ASSEHR), Volume 258. Retrieved on June 29, 2021. Atlantis Press. <https://download.atlantis-press.com/article/55914268.pdf>. 2018.
- [19] Wiwy T. Pulkadang, Hamzah B. Uno, Haris Panal, Keysar Panjaitan, Integrated Learning Module Development on Department of PGSD Students, Gorontalo State University, Indonesia. Journal Article. International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science (IJAEMS) [Vol-6, Issue-7], doi.org/10.22161/ijaems.67.7. Retrieved on June 22, 2021. https://ijaems.com/upload_images/issue_files/7IJAEMS-10720209IntegratedLearning.pdf. July 2020.